

The Role of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in Logistics: Expectations and Challenges in Package Delivery

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <p>Keywords: Environmental impacts Concerns Unmanned aerial vehicle Package delivery Systematic literature review</p> <p>Received: 3 September 2025 Revised: 18 December 2025 Accepted: 22 December 2025</p>	<p>Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) technology is gaining increasing importance in logistics and package delivery processes. The aim of this study is to examine current applications, expectations, and challenges related to the use of UAVs in package delivery. The research evaluated field applications, market shares, and future expectations in package delivery, as well as the challenges encountered (privacy, security, safety, and environmental impacts) through a systematic literature review; the collected data were classified within the framework of thematic content analysis to provide a comprehensive assessment. The findings reveal the contributions of UAV technology to package delivery, its operational limitations, and current developments in the sector. As a result, it has been determined that the integration of UAV technology into package delivery offers significant opportunities, including rapid delivery, operational cost advantages, and access to hard-to-reach areas. Nevertheless, it has been concluded that full potential cannot be achieved without considering factors such as privacy, security, safety, infrastructure requirements, and regulatory constraints. The study aims to provide stakeholders with guidance for strategic planning, policy development, and technology integration processes, as well as to offer comprehensive insights into the future use of UAVs in package delivery.</p>

1. Introduction

Transportation is the process of moving an object or cargo from one specific point to another. This process involves the timely delivery of manufactured products to the required locations to meet customer demands. Historically, transportation has evolved through various stages and has played a significant role in the economic, social, and cultural life of societies. Today, transportation is considered a fundamental element in facilitating individual lives and meeting societal needs (Gerede, 2015).

Transportation, as a fundamental element of the logistics process, aims to meet the demand for the mobility of people and cargo and constitutes a key component of the global economy. In today's global business world, it has become imperative to transport increasing product volumes with high quality and reliability, and to meet

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service needs through more effective distribution methods. Businesses have begun to consider logistics activities not merely as a transportation process but also as a strategic element that creates value.

Rapid changes in markets, product diversity, technology, and the competitive environment have made the logistics process more dynamic. Improving logistics performance increases the competitiveness of businesses and contributes to their operational efficiency. Air cargo transportation is defined as the delivery of goods from one point to another by aircraft, and significant developments have occurred in this field in recent years. The rapid and safe transportation of cargo, particularly those of high value but small in volume and weight, has made air logistics a critical element in the development of the modern economy. The proliferation of e-commerce, the diversification of logistics capabilities, the increase in product volume, and the intensely competitive environment have increased the importance of speed in business processes. This situation has made air cargo transportation a more attractive option (Çalışkan and Erturgut, 2022).

To remain competitive in globalized markets and keep pace with technological advancements, companies must continually provide easier service to their customers and ensure seamless and rapid access to needed products. In this context unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) stand out as a technological solution that provides fast, safe, and cost-effective package delivery. By improving interaction and communication models between retailers and customers, UAVs increase customer satisfaction and strengthen loyalty to specific retailers. These technological advancements make UAVs an effective solution for commercial package delivery and increase the efficiency of online commerce. Therefore, many logistics and e-commerce businesses are turning to the use of UAVs for package delivery (Erdem et al., 2024).

The observed increase in UAV use in package delivery is sparking new discussions regarding security, safety, privacy, ownership, liability, and regulation. With the increasing prevalence of UAV technology in the logistics sector, public adoption of this new delivery method is crucial. The literature review concluded that there are public concerns about privacy, safety, and security regarding package delivery, and a widespread lack of knowledge about UAV-based delivery processes. Public benefit applications, such as express delivery and emergency medical supply transportation, are well-received, raising awareness of the potential benefits of UAVs in logistics. However, despite this positive outlook, concerns persist regarding in-flight video recording, location data processing, and personal data protection during delivery processes. The level of knowledge, areas of use, and potential risks play a significant role in shaping public attitudes toward this technology. In this context, public perception and adoption of UAV use in package delivery are critical to its future proliferation and its emergence as a sustainable solution in the logistics sector (Rao et al., 2016).

This study aims to comprehensively examine the expectations and challenges associated with the use of UAVs in package delivery. The speed, accessibility, and cost advantages that UAV technology can offer in delivery processes are also evaluated, as are current and planned applications and industry developments. Current literature and industry reports reveal a significant increase in the future prospects for UAV use in package delivery. Large logistics companies and e-commerce platforms, in particular, are investing in UAV-based delivery projects to shorten delivery times and increase operational efficiency. Projects such as Amazon Prime Air, UPS Flight Forward, and DHL Parcelcopter are being tested in pilot projects across various countries in areas such as short-haul deliveries, urgent goods, and medical supplies. Furthermore, many countries are developing legal regulations for airspace management and security standards, encouraging collaboration between companies and public authorities. The findings indicate that UAV-based delivery has the potential to become a more integrated solution in the logistics sector in the near future, but that critical challenges such as privacy, data security, flight safety, and noise pollution hinder this process. The risk of misuse of visual and location data collected by UAVs raises concerns about individual privacy; potential technical malfunctions or loss of control pose a threat to both cargo and environmental safety. Noise pollution in residential areas is a significant factor that can negatively impact public acceptance. Consequently, the need to strengthen technical infrastructure, clarify regulatory frameworks, develop security and privacy protocols, and raise public awareness of this technology is emphasized for widespread use of UAVs in package delivery.

2. Conceptual Framework

UAVs are unmanned aerial vehicles that can be remotely controlled or operated autonomously. UAVs can fly at different altitudes and speeds depending on weather conditions thanks to integrated sensors and cameras. UAVs are typically controlled from a ground station. Some models also utilize global positioning systems (GPS) and other navigation systems to provide autonomous flight capabilities (Mohsan et al., 2022).

UAVs have undergone a significant evolution throughout history, leading to radical changes in both military and civilian environments. The history of UAVs dates back to the bomb-carrying balloons used in the Austrian siege of Venice in 1849, and the first applications with control systems in 1916 demonstrated their military potential. After World War II, the effectiveness of UAVs in reconnaissance and surveillance applications increased, with the US SR-71 Blackbird spy plane playing a critical role in the evolution of this technology. UAVs began to be widely used in civilian applications starting in 1991, and their use in civilian airspace began in 2006 with the FAA granting the first commercial permit. In 2013, civilian UAV manufacturer DJI played a significant role in the UAV market with its Phantom series. In the same year, delivery companies began using UAVs for package delivery. Between 2014 and 2016, UAV use expanded, and the FAA introduced regulations for small UAVs. Integration programs were launched between 2017 and 2020, and they were effectively used to protect public health during the pandemic. Amazon launched its autonomous package delivery service with UAVs in 2022. This process demonstrates that UAVs are shaped by technological advancements rather than military needs (Uzuntaş, 2024).

In recent years, technological advances have significantly increased the use of UAVs in both commercial and private sectors, and their application areas have also diversified. UAVs are used in a variety of areas, from agricultural operations to search and rescue operations, from firefighting to cargo transportation (Wang et al., 2023). While the primary focus of this study is cargo transportation, applications of UAVs outside this field are also detailed with examples.

- Agriculture

UAVs are equipped with sensors specifically developed for agricultural applications and are capable of monitoring important parameters such as soil quality, temperature, and humidity. The use of imaging sensors and cameras on UAVs plays a critical role, particularly in precision agriculture. UAVs overcome land limitations in chemical spraying operations, reducing farmers' chemical exposure risks and reducing costs. For example, the use of UAVs has saved 90% of herbicides in corn fields and 43% in sugar beet fields. Half of the rice fields in Japan are sprayed by UAVs. Furthermore, UAV-based counting methods are useful in meeting agricultural inventory needs and identifying plant stress (water, nutrient, and disease stress) (Hassler and Baysal-Gurel, 2019).

- Environmental Monitoring

Research on air, sea, and water pollution enables UAVs to monitor and control environmental events such as global climate change, volcanic eruptions, and marine waste disposal. Water resources polluted by industrial waste can be detected using UAVs. They can also be used to identify unauthorized tree felling, fishing, and hunting outside the hunting season in forest areas (Erdil, 2021).

- Floods

UAVs that monitor currents before a flood can effectively monitor the status of dams. If any risky situations are detected during this monitoring, authorities can quickly intervene. This application of UAVs is highly flexible; flight patrols can be optimized based on time or other workloads. During floods, citizens can be stranded in flooded areas. Because floods are slow-developing disasters, UAVs can provide support to authorities in a variety of ways. Through UAVs, critical information can be quickly obtained regarding the extent of the area's flooding, which buildings are at risk, and where citizens should be evacuated. This ensures the successful execution of the operation (Restas, 2015).

- Media Industry

In the past, reporters had to use helicopters to obtain aerial footage, which was both costly and time-consuming. However, thanks to UAVs, this process has become much easier and more economical. UAVs are less expensive than helicopters, can capture images more safely in risky situations, and provide the ability to reach incident scenes more quickly and obtain instantaneous images. The media's role is critical in meeting the public's need for information. Therefore, accuracy and rapid publication of news are crucial, especially for breaking news. The widespread use of UAVs allows media organizations to report events more effectively. This change has fundamentally transformed the practice of journalism and accelerated the news gathering process. UAVs offer a significant advantage in providing visual information and informing the public, especially during emergencies and disasters (Tilak, 2020).

- Forest Fires

The use of UAVs offers significant advantages in pre-fire hotspot detection, providing real-time information during response, and post-fire monitoring. Identifying hotspots significantly helps fire managers limit the damage caused by fires before civilians report them. In an application conducted in Szendro, Hungary, UAVs flew on predetermined routes, using thermal cameras and sensors to identify hotspots and provide real-time information to control center personnel (Restas, 2013).

- Beach Rescue Applications

Activities to develop lifeguard UAVs stem from several factors. These factors include the increase in tourist numbers and the low ratio of lifeguards to tourists. The increase in water sports activities has increased tourist density on beaches, leading to a higher rate of drowning. Deficiencies in the use of technology in current rescue processes negatively impact the success rate of rescue operations. In this context, the integration of UAVs stands out as an important solution to increase the effectiveness of rescue processes. By providing rapid and effective intervention, UAVs can play a critical role in preventing drownings (Ajgaonkar et al., 2020).

- Applications in Mining Operations

UAVs offer significant advantages in terms of cost, time, and occupational safety in open-pit mining operations. These vehicles are capable of rapid and highly precise measurements in challenging terrain conditions and can produce maps, digital elevation models, and 3D models in a shorter time than traditional methods. The use of UAVs increases efficiency, ensures occupational safety, and reduces costs in applications such as stripping, production rate calculations, and deformation monitoring in mining sites. In this context, UAV-based applications offer a significant opportunity for future developments in the mining sector (Yavuz, 2019).

2.1. The Use of UAVs in Package Delivery and the Impact of E-commerce

E-commerce has created a profound transformation in the shopping process, offering a more convenient, accessible, and faster experience. In 2022, 18.8% of global retail sales were conducted through e-commerce, and this share is expected to rise to 22.6% by 2027. The COVID-19 pandemic significantly accelerated e-commerce activities, leading to a 150% increase in cargo volumes. These developments have paved the way for cargo delivery volumes to grow from 64 billion in 2016 to 161 billion in 2022 and are projected to reach 225 billion by 2028 (Mohamed and Mohamed, 2025).

The rapid rise of e-commerce has increased consumers' demand for faster delivery and lower shipping costs. For instance, approximately 80% of online shoppers in the United States prefer same-day delivery options. However, traditional delivery systems cannot fully meet these expectations for package delivery and incur additional costs for expedited services. In this context, UAV technology offers an important solution for package delivery. UAVs are increasingly used in delivery processes, providing advantages such as shorter delivery times, reduced delays caused by traffic, lower operational costs, and minimized environmental impact. With the growth of e-commerce, UAV-based package delivery systems play a critical role in the logistics infrastructure (Mohamed and Mohamed, 2025).

According to the 2024 UAV market report, UAV volume is projected to increase from 5.42 million units in 2024 to 7.51 million in 2029. The overall UAV market is expected to reach \$30.2 billion in 2024 and reach \$48.5 billion in

2029, with a CAGR of 9.9% from 2024 to 2029. Growth in the UAV market is driven by advancements in lightweight composite materials, increasing flight duration and efficiency. Furthermore, UAVs are influenced by technological advancements, such as the broadening application possibilities provided by innovations in imaging sensors. These dynamics are shaping the future potential of the UAV industry (MarketsandMarkets, 2024).

The e-commerce sector in Turkey has been growing steadily since 2019 and continued its consistent upward trend in 2024. In 2024, the e-commerce volume increased by 61.7% compared to the previous year, reaching 3 trillion TRY, with a total of 5.91 billion transactions. In retail e-commerce, the number of transactions rose by 10.1% to 1.85 billion, while the volume increased by 63.7% to 1.619 trillion TRY. In USD terms, e-commerce volume grew by 274% during the 2019–2024 period, reaching 89.58 billion USD. As of 2024, the share of e-commerce in Turkey's GDP was 6.5%, and its share in total trade was 19.1%, with average basket values of 508 TRY for general e-commerce and 875 TRY for retail e-commerce. These figures clearly demonstrate that e-commerce continues to strengthen under the influence of digitalization and that the sector's growth is sustained (T.C. Ticaret Bakanlığı, 2025).

Delivery activities in Turkey are conducted extensively through parcel lockers, autonomous transport vehicles, electric vehicles, and mobile service units. Although existing legal restrictions support the development of UAV technology for package distribution, they limit the widespread use of these systems in daily delivery operations. In the future, with the establishment of dedicated landing and pickup points for high-rise buildings, an increase in the number of trained UAV pilots, and the adaptation of these systems to the transportation infrastructure, UAVs are expected to play a more active role in individuals' daily lives for package distribution (Toraman and Öz, 2023).

3. Methodology

The aim of this study is to examine the current applications, expectations, and challenges related to the use of UAVs in package delivery. The study focuses on concerns, expectations, and environmental impacts associated with the use of UAV technology in package delivery. Accordingly, a qualitative research approach has been adopted to conduct an in-depth analysis of the relevant literature.

3.1. Research Design

In this study, a descriptive analysis model was employed to systematically review and analyze the existing literature. Within this model, studies on both the current knowledge regarding the use of UAVs in package delivery and more general UAV applications that shed light on this field were examined. The collected data (academic articles, industry reports, news items) were analyzed using content analysis and categorized according to identified thematic structures, enabling a systematic evaluation. This approach allowed for the consolidation of dispersed information in literature and facilitated reaching conclusions aligned with the research objectives.

3.2. Data Collection and Analysis Tools

The document review technique was adopted as the primary data collection tool. In this context, secondary data obtained through a systematic literature review were evaluated using thematic content analysis. During the

analysis process, the data were coded and categorized based on the current applications of UAVs in package delivery in terms of:

- Current applications and expectations of use
- Challenges and concerns in practice
- Environmental impacts of the application

This analytical structure enabled the systematic compilation and evaluation of the obtained findings.

3.3. Data Analysis Procedure

In this study, thematic content analysis was employed to analyze the data. The analysis process was carried out in a stepwise manner to ensure methodological transparency and enhance the credibility of the findings.

In the first stage, all documents in the dataset were read multiple times in line with the research objectives to gain a comprehensive understanding of the literature. During this stage, recurring opinions, application examples, expectations, and various types of concerns related to the use of UAVs in package delivery were identified.

In the second stage, open coding was applied to the identified meaningful text segments. During the coding process, frequently emphasized topics in the literature were labeled conceptually. These codes covered current application examples and expectations, risks related to safety and security, privacy concerns, and evaluations regarding environmental impacts.

In the third stage, the initial codes were systematically reviewed and grouped into higher-order analytical categories based on conceptual similarities. These categories were organized to reflect recurring thematic patterns in the literature and formed the basis of the analytical framework presented in the findings section.

In the final stage, the categories were assessed holistically, and the main analytical dimensions directly related to the research objectives were determined. These analytical dimensions guided the systematic and coherent presentation of the findings.

3.4. Formation of the Analytical Framework

As a result of the data analysis process, an analytical framework was developed based on recurring patterns identified in literature. This framework provides a multidimensional structure encompassing current applications and expectations of UAVs in package delivery, various types of risks and concerns arising during implementation, and the associated environmental impacts.

During the development of the analytical framework, particular attention was given to concepts such as safety, security, and privacy, which were addressed separately in the literature. These dimensions were analytically distinguished for systematic presentation in the findings section. Similarly, environmental impacts were treated as an independent analytical dimension. This approach enabled the findings to be presented in a clear, systematic, and traceable manner, ensuring that the analytical structure is both conceptually coherent and methodologically transparent.

4. Findings

4.1. Current Practices and Expectations

Increasing urbanization, changing consumer behaviors, the rapid development of multi-channel retail, and a growing interest in sustainability have increasingly placed greater emphasis on package delivery. Shifting customer demands have led to speed and flexibility in delivery processes becoming a fundamental expectation rather than a requirement. With the accelerated migration from rural areas to cities, many more people live in cities today than ever before. According to United Nations data, approximately 65% of the world's population is projected to live in cities by 2050. This highlights the need to maintain the quality of life in cities and mitigate urban problems. The effectiveness of package deliveries in cities has become increasingly important, particularly due to increased traffic congestion and the growth in online shopping volume. The intensive use of traditional land-based transportation systems increases traffic congestion and carbon emissions, while

negatively impacting the speed and quality of delivery services. In this context, in line with increasing urbanization and environmental sustainability goals, the use of drones for package delivery is expected to become increasingly popular (Nakiboğlu, 2020).

The need for material and medication transportation in the healthcare sector is a key driver of UAV use. They enable the rapid delivery of medical supplies, particularly in areas with limited accessibility. They can be used for non-urgent deliveries in rural areas where regular visits by healthcare personnel are limited. This accelerates access to healthcare services and contributes to public health. They also contribute to supply chain optimization, improving the efficiency of logistics services. UAVs also enable precise, rapid, and non-destructive collection of measurement and field data.

This capability offers significant advantages in areas such as job verification, certification processes, construction monitoring, site surveys, and 3D mapping. Thanks to programmable flight parameters, they can collect high-resolution data, enabling large-scale data collection in areas such as urban planning, transportation management, crop classification, and yield estimation. Compared to ground-based systems, data collection and transmission can be accomplished faster and more cost-effectively. Energy efficiency is also a prominent advantage of UAVs. Small-scale models typically run on batteries or fuel, consume less energy, and are more portable than manned aircraft, simplifying storage and logistics processes (Kanat, 2023).

The advantages of UAV transportation are summarized as follows:

- **Fast Delivery:** It enables the rapid and direct delivery of urgent medical supplies, medicine, or important documents to their destinations. Because there are no traffic obstructions, delivery times are shorter, and deliveries are more flexible.
- **Remote and Difficult Access:** It offers safe and rapid delivery in areas where ground transportation is difficult, such as mountainous, forest, islands, or disaster areas.
- **Low Cost:** Fuel and personnel costs are low, infrastructure requirements are low, and it offers an economic advantage over traditional land or air transportation.
- **Environmentally Friendly:** Electrically powered UAVs reduce environmental impact with low carbon emissions and noise levels.
- **Air Traffic Management:** Special regulations developed for UAV transportation support the safe and efficient management of air traffic. Thanks to their three-dimensional mobility, they can follow shorter and more direct routes (Kanat, 2023).

Various initiatives have been undertaken globally in the field of package delivery using drones. In 2013, DHL in the UK delivered less than one kilogram of medicine with Parcelcopter. In 2015, Alibaba in China partnered with Shanghai YTO Express to deliver tea to 450 customers in select cities. That same year, SF Express began offering delivery services with Xaircraft drones. In the UK, FPS Distribution completed the first commercial drone delivery in Sheffield. In 2016, Rakuten in Japan delivered golf balls, candies, and drinks to a golf course in Chiba using drones. That same year, Flirtey in New Zealand delivered the world's first pizza by drone, delivered via Domino's Pizza. In China, JD.com established four drone bases in remote areas of Beijing, Jiangsu, Shaanxi, and Sichuan, improving access for local villagers to China's largest sales festival. That same year, Amazon in the UK made its first drone delivery. In 2017, Iceland's largest e-commerce site, AHA, partnered with Flytrex to launch drone deliveries. That same year, Rakuten in Japan began offering drone delivery services in Minamisoma. These examples demonstrate that drone technologies are playing a growing role in the logistics sector, particularly in situations requiring fast, long-distance, and specialized deliveries, and that they are being tested in various countries for various applications. UAV experiences of logistics companies are shown in Figure 1 (Garcia and Santoso, 2019).

Country	Company	Drones provider	Description	Timeline
			Parcelcopter delivered < 1 kilogram medicine	2013 Dec
			Alibaba partners with Shanghai YTO Express to deliver tea to 450 customers around select cities in China	2015 Feb
			SF Express provides delivery services with Xaircraft drones in China	2015 Mar
			FPS distribution completed first commercial delivery using UAV in Sheffield	2015 Mar
			Rakuten delivers golf balls, sweets and drinks at the golf course in Chiba	2016 Apr
			Domino delivers world's first ever pizza by drone in New Zealand	2016 Nov
			JD has launched four drone bases in remote parts of Beijing, Jiangsu, Shaanxi and Sichuan, making it easier for local villagers to tap into China's largest sales festival	2016 Nov
			Amazon made its first drone delivery in UK	2016 Dec
			Iceland largest ecommerce website AHA launched drones in partnership with Flytrex	2017 Aug
			Rakuten provides drone delivery service in Minamisoma city	2017 Oct

Fig. 1: UAV experiences of logistics companies (Garcia and Santoso, 2019)

Additionally, Amazon patented several UAV fulfillment center projects in this area in 2017. One of these is the multi-story distribution center project for UAVs shown in Figure 2. Distribution centers are typically large storage facilities located outside of cities. However, these structures outside of cities make it difficult for UAVs to make deliveries within the center. To address this issue, experts have advocated for the establishment of high-rise UAV distribution centers. In this context, the multi-story distribution center for UAVs, developed and patented, facilitates the delivery of shipments to receiving locations using UAVs. These centers will allow multiple UAVs to take off and land simultaneously. Amazon is also working to allow UAVs to take off and land from moving vehicles, in addition to fixed hubs (Toraman and Öz, 2023).

Fig. 2: Multi-level execution center for unmanned aerial vehicles (Curlander et al., 2017)

UAVs have the potential to revolutionize logistics and e-commerce processes. They enable online retailers to offer their customers fast, affordable, and accessible delivery solutions. Many countries are beginning to experience the practicality of this approach. For example, more than 3,000 packages have been delivered via UAVs in Australia, and a San Francisco-based organization has delivered more than 200 medical supplies to remote health centers in Ghana. Over the next decade, UAVs are expected to increase e-commerce revenues by approximately 25% and save online retailers approximately \$50 million in delivery costs. The impact of UAVs on e-commerce deliveries will be significant, especially considering that deliveries cost less than \$1 and can be completed within 30 minutes. In addition, Skye Air Mobility has secured seven contracts from various healthcare institutions, including AIIMS Jodhpur and AIIMS Rajkot, in January 2024 to use advanced UAV technology for medical supply delivery. These developments demonstrate the growing potential for use of UAVs in the logistics and healthcare sectors (Fortune Business Insights, 2025).

UAV delivery offers faster, more efficient, and potentially lower-cost solutions compared to traditional delivery methods, providing significant opportunities in the food delivery sector. This is particularly relevant in the current context, where the rise in fast commerce has led to increasing consumer demand for shorter delivery times. UAVs can bypass traffic congestion to deliver directly to customers, significantly reducing delivery times, especially in urban areas. The expansion of UAV-based Food Delivery services is also expected to influence access to unhealthy foods and consumption habits. Initially, UAV delivery applications focused on high-value and urgent products, such as medical supplies, but their scope is gradually expanding. Companies are exploring the use of UAVs for delivering retail products, food, and daily necessities. Examples such as Amazon Prime Air, Walmart, and Zipline are pushing the boundaries of what products UAVs can deliver and the regions in which they can operate. For instance, in June 2025, Doordash partnered with Flytrex to launch a UAV-based meal delivery service in the Dallas-Fort Worth metropolitan area. Customers in certain areas of Little Elm and Frisco can now order meals from dozens of local and national restaurants, including Papa John's King Road branch and The Brass Tap, through Flytrex's autonomous UAV fleet (Fortune Business Insights, 2025). Examples of delivery UAVs are presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Example of delivery UAVs (Kanat, 2023)

The UAV delivery services market is analyzed by geographic areas: North America, Europe, Asia Pacific, and other regions. North America continues to be the dominant region in this field, holding the largest UAV delivery services market share by 2024. Market growth in the region is expected to be supported by the increasing adoption of UAV services and the presence of leading UAV manufacturers in the US. With the increasing demand for last-mile logistics and the introduction of innovative technologies, the region is projected to experience significant growth

in the coming years. Growth in the US is driven by the need for more efficient, faster, and cost-effective commodity delivery, particularly in the last-mile delivery segment. Furthermore, advancements in UAV technology, such as longer flight times and higher payload capacities, are expected to further contribute to growth in the region. For example, in January 2024, DroneUp, a leading autonomous UAV delivery and logistics company, announced that it had been approved by the Federal Aviation Administration for beyond-line-of-sight UAV deliveries. Figure 4 illustrates the market size of UAV delivery services in North America (Fortune Business Insights, 2025).

Fig. 4: North America Drone Delivery Service Market Size, 2024 (Fortune Business Insights, 2025)

In Turkey, the use of UAV technology in delivery applications will become increasingly widespread in the future. One of the most important indicators of this is the ever-increasing volume of e-commerce. Figure 5, shows the platforms through which shopping takes place in Turkey, using data from the Ministry of Trade.

Web: 24%, Web Mobile: 6%, Mobile App: 70%

Fig. 5: Distribution of Purchases by Platform (Toraman and Öz, 2023)

Studies conducted in Istanbul reveal an increase in demand for contactless delivery systems in the wake of COVID-19. Research indicates that those who welcome the use of UAVs in deliveries will not experience any

difficulties adapting to this technology. This demonstrates that people are open to technological innovations and that UAVs can be effectively used in delivery processes in the future. The rapid growth of e-commerce has made delivery operations more complex and necessitated the diversification of processes. In this context, the adoption of UAV technology and its integration into logistics processes stands out as a significant development for the sector. UAVs are expected to assume a more active and widespread role in delivery processes in the future (Toraman and Öz, 2023).

4.2. Challenges

4.2.1. Privacy Concerns

Many legal regulations are being developed for the integration of UAVs into national airspaces, but studies on the potential impact of UAV use by the public, individuals, or companies on privacy have been quite scarce. Violation of privacy is one of the primary problems caused by technology and digital systems. An examination of global legislation reveals that the primary reason why UAVs require special permission to fly over residential areas and crowded areas is security. However, examples of UAVs being used in ways that violate privacy are presented in Table 1. This necessitates regulating the issue of "privacy" in legislation regarding the use of UAVs in daily life and conducting a "privacy" impact analysis on UAV use (Kahveci and Can, 2017).

Table 1: Examples of Incidents Where Unmanned Aerial Vehicles Create Privacy Concerns

Year	Event
2014	A woman living in a 26th-floor apartment in Seattle (USA) was enjoying private moments in her bedroom when she encountered a UAV hovering outside her window. This situation evoked a feeling that her privacy had been violated, becoming a striking example of how close a UAV could observe. The UAV's presence was perceived not only as a physical threat but also as a technological tool that intruded into individuals' private lives (Kahveci and Can, 2017).
2015	Observation and recording were conducted via UAV at the Atatürk Girls' Dormitory in the Zeytinburnu district of Turkey. This raised privacy and confidentiality concerns among students and staff at the dormitory (Kahveci and Can, 2017).
2015	During a UAV flight, the aircraft was shot down by another person using a weapon. This attack rendered the UAV unusable, and the UAV pilot took the incident to court, demanding damages from the opposing party. The opposing party argued in its defense that the camera-equipped UAV had flown over its private space without its knowledge, causing a violation of its privacy. The opposing party stated that it had the right to disable the UAV and did not wish to pay the amount of financial compensation. As a result of the case, the court found the UAV pilot's actions unjust. The court deemed this action to be a tort, as a video flight conducted over someone else's private property without the necessary permissions constitutes a violation of the right to privacy, and rejected the UAV pilot's request (Uzuntaş, 2024).
2017	A 27-year-old woman in Darwin was swimming in her backyard pool when she encountered a UAV approximately 10 meters above her and stated that she was deeply shocked by this situation (Butler, 2019).
2017	In Orem, USA, it was revealed that a couple had been observing their neighbors using a UAV. When the UAV was seized, numerous recordings were found showing the interiors of houses in the neighborhood (Scharf, 2019).
2024	Following the surveillance of their opponents by the Canadian women's national team using a UAV for espionage purposes, FIFA imposed a 6-point deduction on the Canadian team, suspended three of its coaches, and fined the team approximately 350,000 dollars (Lewis, 2024).

While UAVs offer significant advantages over manned aircraft and ground-based systems, they also raise privacy concerns. While the use of UAVs has the potential to be particularly effective in emergency situations, privacy violations pose significant public concern. Research suggests that public acceptance of UAVs for security and emergency applications is increasing, but acceptance and privacy concerns are lower for commercial, hobbyist, or routine surveillance applications (Komasová, 2021).

4.2.2. Security Concerns

UAVs have a significant impact on public perception of security. In addition to the advantages offered by UAVs, society also considers their potential risks. In particular, the risk of crashing and uncontrolled flights of UAVs near airports pose serious threats to civil aviation. This increases public security concerns and creates a negative perception of UAVs. Possible accidents at airports and unauthorized intrusions into airspace exacerbate public security concerns and highlight the need for regulations regarding the use of these vehicles. Public perception

of security is a key factor influencing support or opposition to the use of UAVs. In this context, effective regulations and oversight mechanisms are critical to positively impacting public perception of security (Uzuntaş, 2024). Examples of incidents where UAVs have raised security concerns are provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Examples of Incidents Where Unmanned Aerial Vehicles Create Security Concerns

Year	Event
2015	The UAV crashed on the White House lawn, causing security concerns. Following the incident, buildings surrounding the White House were closed for a period of time. It is believed the UAV was flown for recreational purposes.
2015	Drug cartels have attempted to transport drugs using UAVs across the US–Mexico border. A UAV that took off from Mexico crashed in southern California.
2017	In China, at Hangzhou International Airport, a UAV operator was detained for filming landing aircraft from a very close distance. Following the incident, DJI, the manufacturer of the UAV in question, issued a statement strongly condemning this action.
2018	At Auckland Airport in New Zealand, pilots noticed a UAV approaching within 5 meters of a landing Boeing 777-200 and expressed concern that the UAV could be ingested into the aircraft's engines.
2020	Near Madrid Barajas Airport in Spain, a UAV sighting raised security concerns, leading to the temporary closure of one of the four runways at the airport.
2022	During the Russia–Ukraine war, the intensive use of UAVs by both sides has raised security concerns, particularly among civilians.

Although UAVs have great potential in terms of usage, concerns regarding security are inevitable. UAVs pose various risks to public safety, privacy, and overall security. Therefore, future research should address security issues more comprehensively to ensure the societal acceptance of UAVs. Studies on public security concerns related to UAVs indicate that while these vehicles offer significant opportunities in urban environmental management, this potential is limited by safety concerns. For the widespread adoption of UAVs, it is critical that these risks are well understood and effectively managed (Gallacher, 2016; Schmidt and Saraceni, 2024)

4.2.3. Safety Concerns

While the importance of UAVs in the aviation sector has been increasing in recent years, the safety concerns they raise are also increasing. Uncontrolled UAV operation in airspace, particularly when UAVs exceed legal limits and fly at high altitudes, poses a serious threat to air traffic safety. In this context, UAV pilots' lack of knowledge, inadequate knowledge of airspace regulations and legislation, and failure to comply with safe flight practices are among the factors generating public concern (Reddy and DeLaurentis, 2016).

Public safety concerns regarding UAVs are influenced by numerous technical, social, and regulatory factors. Inadequate training or lack of knowledge of UAV pilots exacerbates these concerns. Therefore, pilot training and licensing processes are critical to safety. According to data from the Canadian Department of Transport's Civil Aviation Daily Incident Reporting System, 355 incidents involving UAVs were reported in Canadian airspace between November 5, 2005, and December 31, 2016. Of these incidents, 66.5% involved UAV sightings, while 22.3% involved close encounters with piloted aircraft. A significant increase in similar incidents has been observed since 2013. Most of these reported incidents were reported by aircraft pilots. Although UAVs are generally prohibited in airspaces above 400 feet of the 270 reported incidents, 80.4% occurred above 400 feet, and 62.6% occurred above 1,000 feet. In terms of horizontal distance to the nearest airport, 74.6% of the 268 reported incidents occurred within five nautical miles. This data suggests that UAV incidents in Canada are predominantly caused by airspace violations, and that low cost and rapid proliferation, combined with training deficiencies, increase security risks (Nesbit et al., 2017).

According to a study conducted in the USA, the compliance of UAV users with legislative rules and regulations was examined at the national level. UAVs must operate in harmony with other aircraft, especially in congested airspace. The lack of adequate regulations for air traffic management makes the safe operation of UAVs difficult. Although recreational UAV users are as common as commercial users, they exhibit lower regulatory compliance regarding registration and flight altitude limitations. The research findings revealed that recreational users are less likely to comply with UAV maximum flight altitudes than commercial users. Furthermore, the recreational user population is larger, and professional aviation knowledge is more limited. Therefore, it is recommended that

additional measures be developed to increase regulatory compliance among recreational UAV users (Huang et al., 2021).

4.2.4. Environmental Impacts

The integration of UAVs into delivery processes presents both opportunities and risks in terms of their environmental impacts. UAVs, which offer the potential to reduce carbon emissions thanks to their rechargeable electric power systems, are generally considered an environmentally friendly solution. However, it should be noted that the environmental impacts of UAVs as they integrate into nature and urban life are not limited to their carbon footprint; they can also have direct or indirect impacts on various species and ecosystems. One such impact is the tendency of living creatures to damage UAVs or the objects they transport. For example, another study of UAVs used by Google's subsidiary Wing revealed that the high-frequency noise produced by these vehicles disturbed residents, and even animals reacted to these sounds. This is considered a factor that should not be overlooked in terms of the social integration of technology. The moment a crow attacks a UAV is shown with still images from a video (Figure 6) (Cawthorne and Juhl, 2022).

Fig. 6: Moment of Crow Attack on Coffee Delivery UAV (Cawthorne and Juhl, 2022)

In recent years, while media outlets have highlighted the misuse of UAVs in urban environments, DJI has issued a clear statement addressing these negative perceptions. Survey results indicate that 89% of respondents prefer media and online sources to official sources for information about UAVs. This demonstrates that international news shapes public perceptions of security, safety, and privacy. Privacy concerns are prominent in research on commercial UAV use in smart cities. The potential for privacy violations due to UAVs' ability to capture images and record data raises concerns. Civilian users and regulators are increasingly concerned about the potential for privacy violations and legal changes that will restrict non-commercial uses (Serafinelli, 2022).

Society expects UAV applications to be safe and secure. In this context, it is important for regulatory authorities to conduct strict inspections and improve pilot licensing processes. Society expects greater transparency regarding minimizing risks in UAV applications. To ensure efficient, reliable, and safe flights for UAVs, new regulations and policies need to be developed and implemented. These regulations are crucial for improving the operational safety of UAVs, optimizing airspace management, and ensuring public safety. Furthermore, these policies will support the sustainable integration of UAV technologies and contribute to the growth of the industry. In this context, steps such as determining risk analysis and safety standards, establishing training programs, and strengthening inspection mechanisms should be taken in collaboration with stakeholders. This will maximize the potential of UAVs while preventing potential hazards (Mohsan et al., 2023).

Society expects these applications to increase efficiency and reduce costs. Recommendations include imposing and revising limits on UAV flight altitudes, ensuring flights are carried out on designated routes, promoting renewable energy use and environmentally friendly UAV technologies, and implementing regulations to prevent violations of privacy. To encourage green consumption, governments should encourage other public and private sector representatives to participate in UAV services and inform consumers about the importance of these environmentally friendly services for environmental protection. This will encourage individuals to consider environmentally responsible green behaviors when making purchasing decisions for this technology (Çetin et al., 2022).

There is a need for greater public awareness and understanding of the environmental impacts of UAVs. Suggested opportunities for institutions of higher education to educate the public include developing aviation-focused after-school programs and aviation-related courses, establishing aviation minors to provide students with additional educational opportunities, organizing aviation programs, and organizing summer aviation camps for high school students. These suggestions will contribute to raising education and awareness of the aviation sector, helping to develop future aviation professionals (Keilman, 2019).

5. Conclusion and Discussion

Consumers' attitudes toward UAV deliveries are largely based on their open-minded approach to technological innovations. In this context, technology is expected to bring significant advancements to the logistics sector. However, it is emphasized that factors influencing social acceptance, such as safety, privacy, and environmental impacts, must be carefully considered during the integration process. Therefore, the integration of UAVs into delivery operations should be evaluated not only from a technical perspective but also comprehensively in terms of social and behavioral dimensions.

In conclusion, the integration of UAV technology into air cargo operations offers notable advantages, including rapid delivery, lower operational costs, and access to hard-to-reach areas. The speed provided by UAVs in last-mile deliveries, humanitarian aid activities, and emergency response enhances their overall effectiveness. Nevertheless, regulatory restrictions, safety concerns, infrastructure requirements, and the need for advanced technology continue to pose major challenges for the sector. Additionally, UAV-based transportation is reported to offer environmental benefits by reducing carbon emissions compared to traditional methods. To fully realize this potential, it is critical for governments, businesses, manufacturers, and industry stakeholders to collaborate and adopt a balanced approach between innovation and safety.

Author Statement

All authors contributed equally to the study conception, design, and writing of the manuscript. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

- Ajgaonkar, K., Khanolkar, S., Rodrigues, J., Shilker, E., Borkar, P., & Braz, E. (2020). Development of a lifeguard assists drone for coastal search and rescue. *Global Oceans 2020: Singapore – U.S. Gulf Coast*, 1–10.
- Butler, D. (2019). Drones and invasions of privacy: An international comparison of legal responses. *University of New South Wales Law Journal*, 42(3), 1039–1074.
- Cawthorne, D., & Juhl, P. M. (2022). Designing for calmness: Early investigations into drone noise pollution management. In *2022 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems (ICUAS)* (pp. 839–848).
- Çalışkan, T. B., & Erturgut, R. (2022). Lojistik faaliyetlerde İHA kullanımı: İHA pilotları üzerine bir araştırma. *Uygulamalı Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 4(1), 1–16.
- Çetin, E., Cano, A., Deransy, R., Tres, S., & Barrado, C. (2022). Implementing mitigations for improving societal acceptance of urban air mobility. *Drones*, 6(2), 28.

- Curlander, J. C., Gilboa-Amir, A., Kisser, L. M., Koch, R. A., & Welsh, R. D. (2017). U.S. Patent No. 9,777,502. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- Erdem, M. A., Akdağ, H. C., & Toraman, Y. (2024). Son aşama teslimatta otonom drone kullanımı üzerine bir araştırma. *Yenilik Yolculuğu*, 79(1), 79.
- Erdil, B. (2021). İnsansız hava araçlarının kullanım alanları ile bu araçların Türkiye'nin yurtdışı operasyonlarındaki yeri ve önemi. *Bölgesel Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 5(2), 581–607.
- Fortune Business Insights. (2025). *Drone package delivery market*. Retrieved from <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/drone-package-delivery-market-104332>
- Gallacher, D. (2016). Drones to manage the urban environment: Risks, rewards, alternatives. *Journal of Unmanned Vehicle Systems*, 4(2), 115–124.
- Garcia, O., & Santoso, A. (2019). Comparative evaluation of drone delivery systems in last-mile delivery. *Journal of Unmanned Vehicle Systems*, 7(1), 1–12.
- Gerede, E. (2015). *Havayolu taşımacılığı ve ekonomik düzenlemeler*. Ankara: Sivil Havacılık Genel Müdürlüğü Yayınları.
- Hassler, S. C., & Baysal-Gurel, F. (2019). Unmanned aircraft system (UAS) technology and applications in agriculture. *Agronomy*, 9(10), 618.
- Huang, C., Chen, Y. C., & Harris, J. (2021). Regulatory compliance and socio-demographic analyses of civil unmanned aircraft systems users. *Technology in Society*, 65, 101578.
- Kahveci, M., & Can, N. (2017). İnsansız hava araçları: Tarihçesi, tanımı, dünyada ve Türkiye'deki yasal durumu. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Mühendislik, Bilim ve Teknoloji Dergisi*, 5(4), 511–535.
- Kanat, Ö. Ö. (2023). *Dronelar ve hava kargo faaliyetleri*. Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.
- Keilman, R. (2019). Drones on the rise: Societal misperceptions of small, unmanned aircraft systems (sUAS). *Purdue Undergraduate Research Conference*, 1(1), 1–10.
- Komasová, S. (2021). Possible inspiration: Drone-related literature and its potential for public perception research. *Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems*, 103(3), 54.
- Lewis, S. (2024). *FIFA deducts Canada six points and bans coaches in drone spy scandal*. Retrieved from <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2024-07-28/fifa-deduct-canada-six-points-and-ban-coaches-drone-spy-scandal/104151838>
- MarketsandMarkets. (2024). *UAV (drone) market size, share, trend and growth analysis*. Retrieved from <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/unmanned-aerial-vehicles-uav-market>
- Mohamed, A., & Mohamed, M. (2025). Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in Last-Mile Parcel Delivery: A State-of-the-Art Review. *Drones*, 9(6), 413.
- Mohsan, S. A. H., Khan, M. A., Noor, F., Ullah, I., & Alsharif, M. H. (2022). Towards the unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): A comprehensive review. *Drones*, 6(6), 147.
- Mohsan, S. A. H., Othman, N. Q. H., Li, Y., Alsharif, M. H., & Khan, M. A. (2023). Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs): Practical aspects, applications, open challenges, security issues and future trends. *Intelligent Service Robotics*, 16(1), 109–137.
- Nakiboğlu, G. (2020). Drone taşımacılığı ve son-adım teslimatta kullanımı. *Çukurova Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 24(2), 285–298.
- Nesbit, P. R., Barchyn, T. E., Hugenholtz, C. H., Cripps, S., & Kucharczyk, M. (2017). Reported UAV incidents in Canada: Analysis and potential solutions. *Journal of Unmanned Vehicle Systems*, 5(2), 51–61.
- Rao, B., Gopi, A. G., & Maione, R. (2016). The societal impact of commercial drones. *Technology in Society*, 45(1), 83–90.
- Reddy, L. B., & DeLaurentis, D. (2016). Opinion survey to reduce uncertainty in public and stakeholder perception of unmanned aircraft. *Transportation Research Record*, 2600(1), 80–93.
- Restas, A. (2013). On halfway between the military and civil use: Disaster management supported by UAS applications. *In AUVSI 2013 Exhibition and Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 12–15).
- Restas, A. (2015). Drone applications for supporting disaster management. *World Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 3(3), 316–321.
- Scharf, R. L. (2019). Drone invasion: Unmanned aerial vehicles and the right to privacy. *Indiana Law Journal*, 94(3), 1065.
- Schmidt, S., & Saraceni, A. (2024). Consumer acceptance of drone-based technology for last mile delivery. *Research in Transportation Economics*, 103, 101404.
- Serafinelli, E. (2022). Imagining the social future of drones. *Convergence*, 28(5), 1376–1391.
- T.C. Ticaret Bakanlığı. (2025, May 6). *Türkiye'de E-Ticaretin Görünümü*. Retrieved December 11, 2025, from <https://ticaret.gov.tr/duyurular/turkiyede-e-ticaretin-gorunumu-raporu-yayinlandi-06-05-2025>
- Tilak, G. (2020). Drones and media industry. *RUDN Journal of Studies in Literature and Journalism*, 2(2), 360–366.
- Toraman, Y., & Öz, T. (2023). The use of new technologies in logistics: Drone (UAV) use in last mile delivery. *Sosyoekonomi*, 31(58), 105–124.

- Uzuntaş, K. N. (2024). İnsansız hava araçları: Geçmişten günümüze gelişimi ve barındırdığı riskler. *Scientific Journal of Innovation and Social Sciences Research*, 4(2), 64–81.
- Wang, N., Mutzner, N., & Blanchet, K. (2023). Societal acceptance of urban drones: A scoping literature review. *Technology in Society*, 75, 102377.
- Yavuz, G. (2019). Açık maden işletmelerinde insansız hava aracı (İHA) uygulamaları. *Türkiye Jeoloji Bülteni*, 62(1), 99–112.

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